

ISic0406

I.Sicily inscription 0406

Language

Ancient Greek with the first two lines in Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2013.10.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found on Ortygia 10 May 1792

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 8

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height 105 cm

Width 49.5 cm

Depth 49 cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus**

Text of Manganaro 1994

Translation**Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 284592

EDR 074189

EDCS 21900447

PHI 140305

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